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Republika Srbija

UDK: 347.155(37)
UDK: 347.63-055.621(37)
UDK:316.346.3-053.2:34(37)
UDK: 347.726-053.2(37)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17812958

ZAŠTITA PRAVA DETETA U ANTIČKOM RIMU

Zaštita prava deteta u antičkom Rimu bila je oblikovana složenim spojem pravnih normi, društvenih običaja i porodičnih odnosa. Iako rimsko pravo u početku nije poznavalo savremeni koncept „prava deteta“, postojali su mehanizmi koji su, direktno ili indirektno, uticali na njegov položaj i zaštitu. Da bi dete bilo pravom priznato, i da bi moglo da uživa pravnu zaštitu kao prethodno pitanje nametalo se da li ga je otac porodice na osnovu patria potestas priznao za svoje ili ne, što je podrazumevalo da je reč o detetu rođenom u zakonitom braku. Patria potestas davala je ocu gotovo apsolutnu vlast nad detetom, uključujući odluke o životu, smrti, obrazovanju i imovini (ius vitae ac necis). Vremenom vlast oca porodice bila je ograničavana zakonodavnim reformama i moralnim normama. Takođe, razvoj institucija kao što su tutela i cura obezbeđivao je zaštitu maloletnika bez očeve starateljske vlasti, dok su zakoni poput Lex Plaetoria štitili mlade od ekonomskog iskorišćavanja. Iako su deca u okviru rimskog prava prvenstveno posmatrana kroz prizmu porodične i društvene uloge, rimsko pravo postepeno je uvodilo mehanizme koji su prepoznali ranjivost ove kategorije pravnih subjekata i potrebu za njihovom pravnom zaštitom. Ovaj rad analizira ključne pravne institute, društvene prakse i transformacije koje su doprinele formiranju ranih oblika zaštite prava deteta u rimskom svetu.

Ključne reči: pater familias, patria potestas, dete kao subjekat prava, tutela i cura, pravna zaštita deteta.

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THE PROTECTION OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS IN ANCIENT ROME

The protection of children's rights in ancient Rome was shaped by a complex interplay of legal norms, social customs, and family relations. Although Roman law did not initially recognize the modern concept of "children's rights," there were various mechanisms that directly or indirectly influenced the child's status and protection. In order for a child to be legally acknowledged and enjoy legal protection, the preliminary question was whether the pater familias recognized the child as his own under patria potestas, which presupposed that the child was born within a lawful marriage. Patria potestas granted the father nearly absolute authority over the child, including decisions regarding life, death, education, and property (ius vitae ac necis). Over time, the authority of the pater familias was limited by legislative reforms and moral norms. Furthermore, the development of institutions such as tutela and cura ensured protection for minors who were not under the father's guardianship, while laws such as the Lex Plaetoria protected young people from economic exploitation. Although children were primarily viewed through the lens of family and social roles, Roman law gradually introduced mechanisms that recognized the vulnerability of this category of legal subjects and the need for their legal protection. This paper analyzes key legal institutions, social practices, and transformations that contributed to creating the early mechanisms for children's rights protection in the Roman world.

Keywords: pater familias, patria potestas, child as a subject of law, tutela and cura, legal protection of the child.